

From Surface Transfer Doping to Nitrogen-Assisted Charging in Hydrogenated Nanodiamonds

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Abstract

Hydrogenated nanodiamonds exhibit unusual surface polarity, positive ζ -potential, and strong interactions with water and small molecules, yet the origin of these effects remains debated due to the intertwined roles of lattice disorder and nitrogen incorporation. In particular, detonation and HPHT nanodiamonds are often discussed interchangeably despite fundamental differences in structure and impurity content. Here, we address this ambiguity by introducing low-nitrogen detonation nanodiamonds with a defective structure comparable to conventional DNDs, enabling separation of nitrogen-related and defect-driven effects. Using hydrogen annealing up to 1300 °C combined with spectroscopic, electrokinetic, and thermogravimetric analyses, we examine how hydrogen termination, nitrogen content, and structural quality jointly influence surface charging, hydration, and CO₂ interaction. The study establishes a unified framework linking work function, ζ -potential, vibrational signatures, and interfacial reactivity in hydrogenated nanodiamonds, providing a basis for interpreting their behavior in charge-transfer and environmental applications.

Keywords: Hydrogenated nanodiamonds, Surface transfer doping, Nitrogen-assisted charging, Infrared spectroscopy, Photocatalysis

Highlights:

- Hydrogenation induces positive surface charging in nanodiamonds via a common electronic framework

- Nitrogen enhances charge localization and boosts the zeta potential of DND
- HPHT nanodiamonds exhibit Fano-type phonon–carrier interference
- Low-nitrogen DND exhibits a weak IR response and suppressed charge localization
- The origin of surface charge governs the adsorption and photocatalytic activity of nanodiamonds

1. Introduction

Nanodiamonds (NDs) have emerged as a versatile carbon-based material platform combining exceptional chemical stability, rich surface chemistry, and a set of electronic properties that are uncommon among nanoscale solids. Owing to their robust sp^3 diamond core, NDs withstand harsh chemical and thermal conditions, while their high specific surface area enables extensive and tunable surface functionalization[1]. Beyond this chemical versatility, nanodiamonds, particularly when appropriately surface-terminated, exhibit distinctive electronic behavior, including pronounced surface polarity[2], modified work function[3], and the ability to participate in interfacial charge-transfer processes[4].

Accordingly, the scope of nanodiamond applications has shifted in recent years from largely passive roles, such as mechanical reinforcement[5], lubrication additives[6], or biocompatible carriers[7], toward active functions governed by surface-controlled processes. These include photoemission-based nanodiamond photocathodes[8], photocatalytic[9] and photothermal reactions[10], charge-transfer interfaces in hybrid systems[11,12], and gas-phase redox reactions involving small molecules such as CO_2 [13]. In these emerging applications, the nanodiamond surface is no longer a passive boundary but an active element[14] that mediates adsorption, charge separation, and interfacial reactivity, making a detailed understanding of its physicochemical and electronic properties essential.

Nanodiamonds are commonly categorized according to their synthesis route, with the two most widely used classes being nanodiamonds derived from high-pressure high-temperature synthesis (HPHT NDs) and detonation nanodiamonds (DNDs). HPHT NDs originate from bulk synthetic diamond and typically exhibit high crystallinity, a relatively low density of structural defects, and nitrogen concentrations in the ppm range, resulting in electronic properties that remain comparatively close to those of bulk diamond[15–17].

In contrast, DNDs are formed under extreme, highly non-equilibrium conditions[18], which leads to a markedly different microstructure. DNDs are intrinsically polycrystalline, rich in twin boundaries and lattice distortions, and contain nitrogen at concentrations reaching the atomic percent level, with nitrogen distributed throughout the diamond core and often enriched at defect regions[19]. Spectroscopic and microscopic studies have consistently shown that these structural imperfections give rise to localized electronic states associated with defect-rich DNDs [19], as well as deviations from ideal sp^3 coordination that persist

even in carefully purified DND systems[20–22]. Despite these profound differences in their internal structure and impurity landscape, HPHT NDs and DNDs are frequently treated just as nanodiamonds in the literature, particularly in studies addressing surface chemistry, colloidal behavior, or electronic and photocatalytic properties. This practice implicitly assumes that observations made on one nanodiamond class can be directly transferred to the other. However, given the stark contrast in nitrogen content, defect density, and electronic structure[23], such an assumption is far from trivial. In particular, the electronic response of DNDs is expected to be dominated by defect- and impurity-related states, whereas HPHT nanodiamonds more closely resemble a downsized bulk diamond system. Recognizing and disentangling these intrinsic material differences is therefore essential when interpreting surface-driven and electron-mediated processes in ND-based systems. Hydrogen termination endows diamond surfaces with electronic properties that are fundamentally different from those of otherwise chemically inert sp^3 carbon. Key attributes of hydrogen-terminated diamond, including negative electron affinity and adsorbate-driven surface conductivity (via so-called surface transfer doping), have been comprehensively summarized by Crawford et al.[24]. Within this framework, charge transfer between the hydrogenated diamond surface and ambient adsorbates such as water and oxygen leads to near-surface band bending and hole accumulation layers, making the electronic response of hydrogenated diamond highly sensitive to its environment[25–27].

A direct consequence of this surface-driven electronic structure is the ability of hydrogenated diamond to exchange charge with adjacent media. Zhu et al. demonstrated that hydrogen-terminated diamond can act as a solid-state source of solvated electrons in water under optical excitation enabled by negative electron affinity[28]. Subsequent studies showed that interfacial charge transfer at hydrogenated diamond surfaces can be consistently interpreted in terms of surface-mediated band alignment and redox interactions, linking surface conductivity, work function reduction, and photoinduced charge separation across vacuum, gaseous, and aqueous interfaces[14,29–31].

While the surface transfer doping framework successfully rationalizes the electronic and photochemical behavior of well-defined bulk diamond materials, its manifestation in nanodiamonds is more complex and strongly material-dependent. Although recent photoemission studies have confirmed transfer-doping behavior and solvated electrons production in aqueous environments for hydrogenated HPHT NDs[32,33], highlighting the active electronic role of the ND–water interface, the situation for DND, characterized by extreme lattice disorder, nitrogen incorporation, and pronounced surface chemistry, has remained poorly understood. The combination of hydrogen termination with high curvature, finite size, and heterogeneous structural disorder introduces localized electronic states and alters surface–bulk coupling, leading to charge-transfer pathways, hydration structures, and

carrier dynamics that can markedly differ from those of extended diamond surfaces, even under nominally identical surface termination[17,23].

In aqueous dispersions, hydrogenated nanodiamonds (H-NDs) are frequently reported to exhibit a positive ζ -potential at neutral pH, although the microscopic origin of this behavior remains debated. This behavior is unusual for carbon nanomaterials and cannot be explained within conventional acid–base models of surface charging. Early studies already indicated that hydrogenated nanodiamonds exhibit anomalous colloidal behavior inconsistent with classical surface protonation mechanisms[2,34]. A decisive step toward an electronic interpretation was provided by Petit et al., who demonstrated that surface transfer doping directly mediates both the ζ -potential and colloidal stability of hydrogenated nanodiamonds, linking the positive ζ -potential to electron depletion at the diamond surface rather than to ionizable functional groups[29]. Subsequent work further showed that hydrogenated nanodiamonds induce an unusual hydrogen-bond network in interfacial water, consistent with an electronically polarized surface[3,35].

Alternative interpretations have emphasized the role of non-diamond surface carbon, proposing that protonation of sp^2 -rich surface domains contributes to the positive ζ -potential[36]. More recent studies reconcile these views by showing that a positive ζ -potential emerges only when H-NDs retain a sufficiently developed diamond electronic structure, while surface disorder, defects, and sp^2 -rich regions modulate its magnitude and stability[17,37]. These incremental results indicate that the colloidal properties of H-NDs represent a macroscopic manifestation of the distinctive electronic properties of hydrogen-terminated diamond surfaces, further modulated by nanoscale-specific features of the nanodiamond material.

Interpretation of the electronic and photochemical properties of NDs is complicated by the intrinsic coupling between nitrogen incorporation and lattice disorder in DNDs, whereas both factors are inherently low in HPHT ND materials. Thus, comparisons between DNDs and HPHT NDs inevitably mix the effects of nitrogen-related electronic states with those arising from structural defects and lattice imperfections.

In bulk diamond, nitrogen is well known to form deep donor levels and is ineffective as an n-type dopant, acting primarily as a charge-carrier trap rather than a source of free electrons [38]. Despite this established understanding, the potential role of nitrogen in governing the electronic and interfacial behavior of detonation nanodiamonds has received limited direct attention, even though their nitrogen content typically reaches atomic percent levels. Previous studies have primarily focused on controlling or increasing nitrogen incorporation in DNDs [39,40], while reports addressing the opposite limit, i.e., DNDs with reduced nitrogen content, remain scarce [41].

Consequently, the origin of the pronounced interactions of DNDs with water, CO_2 , and photoinduced charge carriers has remained ambiguous. In the absence of suitable

reference materials, observed differences in electronic, colloidal, or photocatalytic behavior could not be unambiguously attributed either to nitrogen-related electronic states or to the high density of defects intrinsic to DNDs. Resolving this ambiguity requires NDs in which nitrogen content and structural disorder can be varied independently, a condition that has not been met in previous studies.

In this work, we address this long-standing ambiguity by systematically comparing three ND systems that decouple nitrogen content from structural disorder: conventional DNDs with typically high nitrogen content (~2 at.% N), low-nitrogen DND (<0.2 at.% N) of comparable size and defective structure, and single-crystalline HPHT NDs (0–30 nm, median size 18 nm) as a reference material. Using hydrogen annealing in H₂ over a broad temperature range (500–1300 °C) combined with mass spectrometry (MS), Raman and FTIR spectroscopy, and Kelvin probe measurements, we correlate nitrogen content with hydrogenation kinetics, resistance to graphitization, hydration behavior, and charge-transfer characteristics. We show that nitrogen critically influences the evolution of electronic properties during hydrogenation, affecting the work function, the emergence of a positive ζ -potential, and the interaction of hydrogenated nanodiamonds with water and CO₂.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Standard, nitrogen-rich detonation nanodiamonds (further abbreviated as **DND**) were prepared by detonation synthesis using a TNT/RDX (40/60) explosive mixture in OZM Research s.r.o., following established industrial procedures. This conventional DND material is broadly available worldwide from several industrial producers. DND are characterized by a nominal primary particle size of ~5–6 nm and a nitrogen content of approximately 2 at.%. A novel, DND sample with a reduced nitrogen content of ~0.2 at.% as determined by elemental analysis was also provided by OZM Research as an experimental material (further abbreviated as **DND low_N**). This material served as a defective detonation nanodiamond material with low nitrogen content. This sample is available upon reasonable request from the provider.

Monocrystalline **HPHT NDs** were provided by Pureon (MSY 18, 0–30 nm), which served as a low-defect, single-crystal nanodiamond material with low nitrogen content. All chemicals were used as received unless stated otherwise, and deionized water (18.2 M Ω ·cm) was used for all aqueous preparations.

2.1.1. Hydrogenation of Nanodiamonds

Before hydrogenation, all the ND samples were oxidized by annealing in the air. All DND powders were annealed in ambient atmosphere at 450 °C for 30 min, while HPHT NDs were

oxidized at 450 °C for 5 h, in line with previously reported protocols[16]. This treatment effectively removed a significant fraction of non-diamond carbon and introduced oxygen-containing surface functional groups. Hydrogenation was carried out by thermal annealing in flowing hydrogen at atmospheric pressure. Oxidized NDs were hydrogenated at 500-1300 °C for 6 h in a tube furnace, using a 100 mg batch to ensure consistency. The hydrogen flow rate was maintained at 5 L·min⁻¹. After hydrogenation, the samples were allowed to cool to room temperature under a hydrogen atmosphere before exposure to air. The resulting samples are referred to as hydrogenated nanodiamonds throughout the whole article (**DND**, **DND low_N** and **HPHT ND**).

2.1.2. Preparation of ND colloids

ND colloids were prepared by dispersing nanodiamond powders in deionized water at concentrations of 1-4 mg/mL, depending on the specific analysis requirements. The dispersions were treated by probe sonication using a rod-type ultrasonic processor operated at 200 W for 1 h (Hielscher UP200St). No centrifugation or size-selection steps were applied. This procedure was used consistently for all nanodiamond types to ensure comparability between samples.

2.2. Structural and Chemical Characterization

2.2.1. Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy was employed to assess the bonding structure and the presence of sp²-related carbon phases. Raman spectra were recorded using a Raman spectrometer (Renishaw InVia) equipped with a 325 nm excitation laser. The laser power at the sample was kept below 0.5 mW to avoid laser-induced heating or graphitization. Spectra were collected in a backscattering geometry using a 100× objective.

2.2.2. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

XPS was used to analyze elemental composition and chemical bonding states. XPS measurements were performed in a Kratos AXIS Supra photoelectron spectrometer by using a monochromated Al K α source (1486.6 eV). The overall energy resolution was 0.45 eV as obtained from the Ag 3d_{5/2} photoelectron peak measurement. The angle of 54° between the incident X-ray beam and the photoelectron analyzer (at normal emission geometry) was fixed for all measurements. High-resolution spectra of the C 1s, O 1s, and N 1s regions were acquired with a pass energy of 10 eV. The positions of core levels were calibrated to the C 1s peak maxima at 285 eV. The chemical composition was determined from the integrated core level intensities after subtracting the Shirley inelastic background. The intensities were normalized by the corresponding sensitivity factors (included in the ESCA software from Kratos). Core-level peaks were fitted with Gaussian functions.

2.2.3. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM)

HRTEM was carried out on a transmission electron microscope JEOL JEM 2200FS operated at 200 kV (Schottky field-emission gun, point resolution 0.19 nm) with an in-column energy Ω -filter for EELS/EFTEM, a STEM unit, and an Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) SDD detector Oxford Instruments X-Max attached. Images were recorded on a Gatan CCD camera with a resolution of 2048 \times 2048 pixels using the Digital Micrograph software package. For HRTEM analysis, the TEM grids were briefly immersed in the respective ND colloid (0.2 mg·mL⁻¹) and let dry prior to introduction into the TEM chamber.

2.2.4. Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS)

SAXS analysis was conducted on a SAXSess instrument (Anton Paar) equipped with a microfocus X-ray source with a Cu anode (Xenocs), single-reflection X-ray optics (Xenocs) and an advanced collimation block. The range of the scattering vector magnitude, q , was 0.18–10 nm⁻¹, enabling analysis of particles up to approximately 20 nm in size and periodic structures up to about 30 nm. The scattering vector magnitude q is defined as $q = (4\pi/\lambda) \sin \theta$, where λ is the X-ray wavelength (0.1542 nm for Cu K α radiation) and θ is the Bragg angle (half of the scattering angle). The powder samples were measured sealed in scotch tape. Due to the high scattering intensity of the samples, the exposure time to X-rays was on the order of minutes. Imaging plates (storage phosphor screens) served as detectors and were read out using a Cyclone[®] Plus Storage Phosphor System (PerkinElmer). The 2D scattering patterns obtained were azimuthally averaged with the instrument software to yield 1D scattering profiles. The resulting 1D profiles were subsequently processed in the *Irena* software package[42]. The processed profiles were fitted with appropriate models using the *Unified Fit*[43] instrument implemented in *Irena*. The volume-weighted average sizes (d) of the primary particles were determined from the gyration radii (R_g) obtained from model fitting in *Irena* assuming spherical particle geometry, i.e. according to the formula: $d = 2R_g\sqrt{5/3}$ [44].

2.2.5. Electrophoretic light scattering, zeta potential

ζ -potential of nanodiamond dispersions were determined using a dynamic light scattering instrument (Zetasizer Nano ZS, Malvern Panalytical, UK) operating with a 633 nm He–Ne laser in a backscattering configuration (173°). The refractive index of diamond ($n = 2.4$) and the viscosity of water at 25 °C (0.890 mPa·s) were used for data evaluation. The ζ -potential was derived from electrophoretic mobility measurements using the Henry equation as implemented in the instrument software. Reported ζ -potential values correspond to the average of three independent measurements. All measurements were performed in

disposable ζ -potential measurement cells. Concentration of the samples was kept at 1 mg·mL⁻¹.

2.2.6. Workfunction (WF) measurement

WF measurement was done by a Kelvin probe system (KPTechnology) placed in a grounded Faraday cage under full dark conditions. The measurements were set to maintain the amplitude of the generated AC voltage depending on the applied DC voltage gradient at 300, which ensured the constant probe-sample distance. WF of the probe was calibrated by evaluation of measured values on a set of metal films (Au, Ti, Ni, Pd, In, Al) to overcome possible discrepancies in reported WF values and local variations for single materials. Based on this procedure, the WF of the golden probe (circular disk of 2 mm in diameter) was estimated to be 5.15 eV. Each reported value is an average of 50 subsequent readouts. For the KP measurements, NDs were drop-casted on gold substrates (thermally evaporated 100 nm Au film on silicon) and thermally annealed on a hotplate at 120°C for 30 min to desorb the surface-bound water.

2.2.7. Mass spectrometry (MS)

Simultaneous differential thermal analysis (DTA), thermogravimetry (TGA), and evolved gas analysis (EGA) using mass spectrometry (MS) at non-isothermal conditions were performed using a simultaneous thermal analyzer Setaram Themys 24 and a quadrupole mass spectrometer Pfeiffer Vacuum OmniStar GSD 320. The powder DND and HPHT ND samples of weight ca. 6-7 mg were measured in an alumina crucible in the temperature range 25-800 °C under an argon atmosphere (purity 6.0N) at the heating rate of 10 K min⁻¹. The empty alumina crucible was used as a reference. Before each DTA-TGA-MS measurement, the oxygen content had to be eliminated by introducing a vacuum and an inert gas (Ar) refill. The apparatus was calibrated in 25–1600 °C using standards Al, Ag, Au, Pd, and Ni. The standard deviation of the performed calibration is around ± 0.8 °C. The blank run (baseline) was measured before the measurement. The Pfeiffer Vacuum OmniStar GSD 320 is a quadrupole mass spectrometer equipped with a controlled and heated anti-corrosive quartz capillary for coupling with Themys 24, yttria coated iridium filament as a source of ionization and fragmentation of evolved gases, secondary electron multiplier as a detector (detection limit < 1 ppm of gases), and a turbo drag pumping system with an interstage turbo pump and diaphragm pump as a vacuum source. The spectrometer enables the detection of atomic masses in the 1–300 amu range. The measurements were conducted in multiple ion detection regime (MID) with a gas flow 1–2 cm³·min⁻¹, 850–1450 V at the SEM detector, mass a detection dwell of 50 ms, resolution 50, and the m/z range 1–100 amu. The obtained data were processed using the Calisto Processing program. For improved clarity, MS ion currents were baseline-corrected by subtracting a linear background determined from temperature

regions without detectable desorption, before normalization by sample mass and specific surface area.

2.2.8. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy in transmission geometry was performed using a Bruker Vertex 70v spectrometer equipped with a KBr beamsplitter and a liquid nitrogen-cooled MCT detector. The measurement chamber was evacuated using a rotary pump to minimize contributions from atmospheric water vapor and CO₂. ND samples were measured in the form of aqueous colloidal dispersions (4 mg·mL⁻¹), which were drop-cast (40 μL) onto CaF₂ mirrors and briefly dried on a hot plate at 80 °C to remove residual water. A clean CaF₂ mirror was used to record a background. Each spectrum represents an average of 128 scans collected in the spectral range of 4000–800 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

Temperature-dependent desorption experiments were carried out on the same spectrometer using complementary FTIR configurations. First, diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS) measurements were performed using a Praying Mantis diffuse reflectance accessory (Harrick Research). Nanodiamond samples were measured as powders after equilibration with ambient air for one week. Before measurement, the powders were gently mixed with spectroscopic-grade NaCl, which served as an inert, diffusely scattering matrix. During the experiment, the chamber was continuously purged with dry nitrogen. The DRIFTS measurements were performed during stepwise heating from room temperature to 300 °C in 25 °C increments. Heating between successive temperature steps was rapid (10–20 s). At each temperature, the sample was equilibrated for 6 min before spectral acquisition, with a typical acquisition time of approximately 90 s.

Second, attenuated total reflection (ATR) FTIR measurements were also conducted on a Bruker Vertex 70v spectrometer using a diamond ATR accessory (Specac) operated in a temperature-dependent mode. Air-equilibrated nanodiamond powders were placed directly onto the ATR crystal and pressed with a constant force using a stainless-steel cone. The effective contact area of the sample was approximately 2 × 2 mm. Temperature control was achieved using an automated heating unit with a ramp rate of 10 K·min⁻¹. After reaching a maximum temperature of 200°C, the heating was switched off, and spectra were collected during free cooling down to room temperature.

To selectively probe water adsorption, selected experiments were performed in which previously heated, adsorbate-free DND powders were exposed to a flow of humidified argon (1 slm, RH 90-100%), and the evolution of IR absorption features was monitored.

Finally, hydrogenated HPHT nanodiamonds were investigated by specular-apertured grazing angle (SAGA) FTIR spectroscopy using a Thermo Nicolet iS50 spectrometer equipped with a KBr beamsplitter and a liquid nitrogen-cooled MCT detector. Measurements were carried

out at an incident angle of 80°. The measurement chamber was continuously purged with dried air to suppress water vapor contributions. Each spectrum represents an average of 128 scans collected in the range of 4000–1000 cm^{-1} with a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . ND colloids (50 μL , 4 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) were drop-cast onto Au-coated and Al-coated Si substrates and briefly heated at 100 °C for 60 s to evaporate the solvent. Corresponding bare Au and Al substrates were measured as background references before each sample measurement.

2.2.9. Photothermal CO_2 reduction

Photothermal CO_2 reduction experiments were carried out using a custom-designed stainless-steel batch photoreactor equipped with a fused-quartz window for illumination. Approximately 20 mg of sample (DND and HPHT ND) were placed in a stainless-steel sample holder positioned at the centre of the reactor. Heating was supplied from below using an external heating plate fitted with two 50 W heating cartridges, providing uniform thermal input to the reactor. The reaction temperature was monitored and controlled using a thermocouple inserted beneath the sample, positioned between the heating plate and the reactor body to accurately measure the photocatalyst bed temperature.

Scheme 1. Graphical representation of the photothermal reaction setup used for CO_2 conversion experiments. Gas-handling system equipped with mass flow controllers (MFCs) for N_2 , CO_2 , and H_2 , connected to the photothermal reactor, pressure gauge, vacuum pump, and gas chromatograph (GC) (a). Schematic view of the photothermal reactor showing the catalyst holder, external light source, thermocouple, and heating cartridges enabling simultaneous optical illumination and temperature control (b).

Before each experiment, the sealed reactor was evacuated to 0 bar absolute to remove residual air. The system was then heated to 200 °C under vacuum and maintained for 2 h to remove adsorbed water and surface contaminants. After activation, CO_2 gas (research

grade, 99.999%, BOC) and H₂ (generated using a Peak Scientific H₂ generator) were mixed in a 1:3 CO₂/H₂ ratio using mass flow controllers (OMEGA, FMA-2617A-V2). The mixture was passed through the reactor for 30 min to let the internal atmosphere equilibrate. The reactor was then pressurised to ~1.8 bar with the same gas mixture and sealed. Illumination for photothermal experiments was provided using a 300 W Xe arc lamp (LSH302, LOT Quantum Design) directed through the quartz window. The lamp was positioned 6 cm above the catalyst surface, delivering an irradiance of 2 suns (~200 mW cm⁻²). Photothermal reactions were conducted for 5 h at 200 °C under continuous illumination. Thermal-only and photo-only control experiments were performed under identical conditions, with either light or heat supplied exclusively, respectively. Additional control tests were carried out under N₂ (N6.0, 99.999%, BOC) and H₂ atmospheres to confirm the carbon source of the detected products. After each reaction, gaseous products were analysed using an Agilent 7890B gas chromatograph equipped with TCD and FID detectors. All experiments were repeated three times using fresh catalysts to confirm repeatability.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural and Size Characterization of Nanodiamonds

Figure 1. High-resolution TEM images of HPHT ND (left), DND low_N (middle), and DND (right). HPHT ND shows single-crystalline particles with coherent lattice fringes. Both DND types exhibit predominantly defect-rich, polycrystalline structures with twinning and lattice distortions, with occasional single-crystalline particles visible in the second row. The top and middle panels show 10×10 nm regions; the bottom panels display 5×5 nm magnified views of representative particles.

Figure 1 shows high-resolution TEM images of HPHT ND (left), DND low_N (center), and DND (right). The HPHT nanodiamonds show atomically resolved lattice fringes with long-range coherence and uniform spacing, characteristic of single-crystalline particles viewed along a low-index zone axis. No lattice bending, mosaicity, or defect features are observed within the imaged regions, consistent with the well-ordered structure expected for single-crystalline HPHT-synthesized diamond. In contrast, both DND low-N and DND exhibit the characteristic structural heterogeneity of detonation-synthesized nanodiamond. Most particles in both samples contain multiple crystalline domains separated by lattice distortions, such as twinning, stacking faults, grain boundary-like features, and local lattice rotations. These defects permeate the particles rather than being confined to a surface layer, confirming that both DNDs are intrinsically polycrystalline and structurally disordered throughout their entire volume [19]. Occasional nearly single-crystalline DND particles are also observed; examples are shown in the second row of the DND low-N and DND columns, yet these are the exception rather than the rule. Importantly, the defect types and overall structural heterogeneity in DND low-N and DND appear highly similar, indicating that their microstructural character is essentially comparable.

Figure 2. Representative SAXS profiles of HPHT ND, DND_low N, and DND samples (a). Volume-weighted particle size distributions of DND_low N and DND samples obtained from the SAXS data (b).

Figure 2 shows the SAXS profiles of HPHT ND, DND_low N, and DND samples (a) and the derived volume-weighted particle size distribution of DND_low N and DND samples (b). SAXS analysis revealed typical scattering profiles for both DND samples, characterized by a knee at approximately 1 nm^{-1} . At higher q values (to the right of the knee), the intensity followed a power-law decay with an exponent of about -4 , consistent with Porod's law ($I \propto q^{-4}$). In the low- q region (to the left of the knee), an approximate power-law behavior with an exponent between -1 and -2 was observed, indicative of fractal aggregates with relatively low density [45,46]. For the HPHT ND sample, only a knee followed by a Porod slope was observed, while the power-law regime associated with aggregates lay outside the instrumental q -range. Nonetheless, it is clear from the HPHT ND SAXS profile that the size of primary particles is substantially larger than in the case of the DND samples (Figure 2a). The resulting average primary particle sizes obtained using Irena software were 7.0 nm for DND, 5.9 nm for DND low_N, and 16 nm for HPHT ND. The SAXS results, therefore, indicate that the average particle size in DND low_N is slightly smaller than in DND, but still comparable, and that the average particle size of HPHT ND is relatively well within specification.

3.2. Thermal Evolution of Surface Chemistry and Thermal Stability of Nanodiamonds

Treatment of nanodiamond powders in a hydrogen atmosphere results in the desorption of surface oxygenated groups and the formation of C-H_x surface terminations via a radical-driven mechanism [47,48]. Replacing heavier oxygen atoms with lighter hydrogen leads to a measurable reduction in weight. Up to $\sim 800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the mass loss of all samples primarily reflects efficient surface hydrogenation, as shown in Figure 3a. For HPHT ND and DND low_N, the residual mass then remains nearly constant between $800\text{--}1000^\circ\text{C}$, indicating a thermally stable hydrogenated surface. In contrast, DND continues to lose mass above $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with an accelerated decrease beyond $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, related to an increased rate of graphitization and subsequent gasification of sp^2 -carbon fragments in the hydrogen atmosphere. At temperatures above $1100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, both DND low_N and HPHT ND also exhibit accelerated weight loss, reflecting the onset of graphitization and subsequent gasification that occurs at higher temperatures than in DND. The correspondence between the temperatures of increased mass loss and the onset of graphitization (see Raman data below) confirms that nitrogen incorporation markedly lowers the thermal stability of DND. Despite pronounced differences in particle size and structural disorder, DND low_N behaves thermally almost identically to HPHT ND, unambiguously demonstrating that nitrogen

incorporation, rather than size or microstructural defects, is responsible for the reduced thermal stability of DND under the applied hydrogenation conditions.

Figure 3. (a) Residual mass, (b) oxygen concentration (XPS), (c) nitrogen concentration (XPS) of HPHT ND, DND low_N, and DND as a function of hydrogenation temperature. (d) High-resolution XPS spectra of C 1s, O 1s, and N 1s of DND as a function of the hydrogenation temperature in °C.

The oxygen concentrations determined by XPS are shown in Figure 3b. All oxidized NDs initially contain ≈ 11 at.% O, typical for air-annealed ND surfaces[20,49]. After hydrogenation at 500 °C, the oxygen level drops sharply in all samples, but most strongly in DND (from ≈ 11 to ≈ 6 at.%). HPHT ND and DND low_N exhibit smaller decreases to ≈ 7 at.%. At 800 °C, their O content falls down to 1 at.%, whereas DND retains ≈ 2 at.% O up to 1200°C. The persistence of oxygen in DND cannot be attributed solely to residual surface species, since hydrogenation efficiently removes oxygen functionalities from the other two materials. This

suggests partial incorporation of oxygen into the diamond lattice, possibly promoted and/or associated with nitrogen-related defects.

The nitrogen concentrations determined by XPS are shown in Figure 3c. HPHT ND typically exhibits substitutional nitrogen levels of ~100–300 ppm (≈ 0.01 - 0.03 at. %) in Type Ib HPHT diamonds[50]. Such a low concentration is below the XPS detection limit; therefore, in our case, HPHT ND shows ≈ 0 at.% N. DND low_N contains ≈ 0.2 at.% N, which is about one order of magnitude lower than the ≈ 2 at.% N found in the conventional DND. The nitrogen content remains essentially constant across the full hydrogenation temperature range in all samples, confirming that nitrogen is structurally incorporated in the diamond lattice or defect network without being lost via surface desorption. Only in DND low_N is a slight decrease in N concentration observed above ~ 1000 °C; one possible explanation is that nitrogen may be unevenly distributed (e.g., enriched in smaller particles or more defective regions), and the weakest N-rich fragments may graphitize and desorb earlier than the main matrix when heated in a hydrogen atmosphere.

High-resolution XPS spectra (Figure 3d) illustrate the chemical evolution of the C 1s, O 1s, and N 1s regions for the DND sample. The C 1s region shows a marked reduction of the C=O and C–O shoulders already between 500–600 °C, while the main peak corresponding to sp^3 -C becomes more intense and stabilizes at 285 eV as the hydrogenation temperature increases. A notable evolution of the CH_x component is also observed, with its intensity increasing with hydrogenation temperature. Above ~ 1100 °C, a pronounced sp^2 -carbon component grows and dominates by ~ 1300 °C, consistent with extensive graphitization and gasification. The N 1s spectra feature two principal components at ~ 398 – 399 eV (attributed to substitutional nitrogen) and ~ 401 – 402 eV (graphitic/pyridinic nitrogen). Their persistence up to ~ 1200 °C corroborates the data in Figure 3c, confirming that nitrogen is an integral part of the diamond or disordered-carbon network.

3.3. Raman spectroscopy analysis

3.3.1. Comparison of Initial Oxidized Nanodiamonds

Raman spectroscopy provides insight into the structural quality of nanodiamonds and the relative contributions of sp^3 - and sp^2 -bonded carbon. Figure 4 compares the Raman spectra of the initial oxidized HPHT ND, DND low_N, and nitrogen-rich DND samples before any hydrogenation. HPHT ND exhibits a sharp diamond Raman line at 1332 cm^{-1} with a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of 16 cm^{-1} , characteristic of a well-ordered single-crystalline diamond lattice. Only a weak G band near 1590 cm^{-1} is observed, indicating a minor contribution of surface-related sp^2 carbon.

DND low_N displays a moderately downshifted and broadened diamond peak centered at 1329 cm^{-1} (FWHM = 25 cm^{-1}), reflecting increased lattice disorder relative to HPHT ND while still preserving a predominantly sp^3 -bonded diamond core. Importantly, despite their slightly

smaller average particle size determined by SAXS (Figure 2), the position and width of the diamond peak in DND low_N remain closer to those of HPHT ND than to DND. This observation indicates that phonon confinement effects do not play a dominant role here; instead, the Raman response is governed primarily by intrinsic lattice disorder and defects rather than the particle size. This is clearly consistent with the recent findings[20,51]. The G band in DND low_N is more pronounced and resolves into two components: a dominant graphitic contribution at $\sim 1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a weaker defect-related band near 1640 cm^{-1} . The relative prominence of the $\sim 1590\text{ cm}^{-1}$ component suggests the presence of interparticle or grain-boundary sp^2 carbon, associated with the aggregate structures inferred from SAXS. In DND, the diamond line further shifts to lower wavenumbers and broadens significantly (1324 cm^{-1} , $\text{FWHM} = 33\text{ cm}^{-1}$). A pronounced low-frequency shoulder around 1250 cm^{-1} , together with strong bands near 1590 and 1640 cm^{-1} , indicates a substantially higher defect density and an increased fraction of non- sp^3 carbon distributed not only at the particle surface but also within the particle interior [19]. The enhanced relative intensity of the $\sim 1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band compared to DND low_N points to a higher density of isolated point defects [52], which may be associated with nitrogen and oxygen-related lattice distortions. Overall, a comparison of the Raman spectrum of DND with DND low_N shows that nitrogen-related lattice defects are the main factor reducing the apparent “quality” of diamond in DND Raman spectra.

Figure 4. Raman spectra of initial oxidized ND samples: HPHT NDs, DND low_N, and DND, with spectral components fitted. Green: a low-frequency shoulder of the diamond peak

($\approx 1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$), red: the diamond peak ($1324 - 1332\text{ cm}^{-1}$), blue: sp^2 -C graphitic ($\approx 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$), purple: sp^2 -C isolated ($\approx 1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$).

3.3.2. Temperature-Dependent Raman Evolution during Hydrogenation

Figure 5 shows the Raman spectra of HPHT ND, DND low_N, and DND after hydrogenation between 500 and 1300°C (panels a–c), together with the corresponding $I_{\text{Dia}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratios (panels d–f), which qualitatively express “nanodiamond quality” and the degree of graphitization. For HPHT ND, hydrogenation up to 600°C induces only minor spectral changes. Between 700 and 1100 °C, a slight increase and subsequent stabilization of the intensity of the G band is observed, corresponding to the $I_{\text{Dia}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio, which remains almost constant up to 1100 °C, reflecting stable surface rearrangement associated with the removal of oxygen-containing groups. Above 1100°C, both D and G bands increase sharply ($I_{\text{Dia}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio decreases), signaling the onset of graphitization that coincides with accelerated mass loss (Figure 3a). DND exhibits clearly different behavior, characteristic of an earlier increase of the G-band intensity already at 600 °C, indicating the onset of surface reorganization under hydrogenation. A distinct D band appears by ~ 800 °C, consistent with surface graphitization onset[53]. The diamond signal progressively weakens and disappears above ~ 1000 °C, in agreement with the strong mass loss observed in Figure 3a. DND low_N (Figure 3b) exhibits a Raman response closely resembling that of HPHT ND. Upon hydrogenation up to ~ 800 – 900 °C, only moderate spectral changes are observed, with a gradual increase of the G-band intensity and a relatively slow decrease of the $I_{\text{Dia}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio (Figure 3e). The Raman diamond peak close to 1330 cm^{-1} remains clearly detectable to higher temperatures than in DND. Taken together, the Raman results demonstrate that nitrogen, and likely also oxygen, incorporation promotes earlier diamond lattice deterioration and graphitization during hydrogenation. This trend is fully consistent with the mass-loss behavior shown in Figure 3a, where DND exhibits accelerated weight loss at significantly lower temperatures, as well as with the XPS data (Figure 3b–d), which reveal the early emergence of sp^2 -carbon components and persistent non-diamond carbon in DND. In contrast, DND low_N remains structurally stable over a substantially broader temperature window, closely resembling the behavior of HPHT ND. The mutual agreement between Raman spectroscopy, XPS, and gravimetric analysis confirms that the reduced thermal and structural stability of DND is governed primarily by nitrogen-related chemical effects rather than by particle size or intrinsic structural disorder alone.

Figure 5. Raman spectra of the HPHT ND (a), DND low_N (b) and DND (c) as a function of the hydrogenation temperature in °C. $I_{D_{ia}}/I_G$ ratio for HPHT ND (d), DND low_N (e) and DND (f) qualitatively expresses the diamond quality and the degree of graphitization as a function of the hydrogenation temperature in °C.

3.4. Infrared Spectroscopy and Thermal Desorption Analysis

3.4.1. Transmission FTIR Spectroscopy of Surface Chemistry Evolution

Figure 6 presents the FTIR spectra of HPHT ND, DND low_N, and DND as a function of hydrogenation temperature. The initial oxidized samples exhibit nearly identical spectra[16,20] dominated by oxygen-containing surface groups: mainly hydroxyl and carboxyl functionalities[49], consistent with the high oxygen content (~10 at.%) determined by XPS (Figure 3b). Upon hydrogenation, these oxygen-related bands progressively diminish and are replaced by C–H stretching features near 2850–2960 cm⁻¹, characteristic of hydrogenated diamond surfaces. The rate and extent of this transformation depend strongly on the ND type. In HPHT ND and DND low_N, removal of C=O species proceeds gradually, and full hydrogenation is achieved at ~800 °C. The spectra between 800–1100 °C remain nearly unchanged, defining an optimal temperature window for efficient hydrogenation while preserving structural integrity, which is consistent with Raman and XPS analyses, and mass-loss data.

In contrast, the DND undergoes more rapid deoxygenation: the C=O band nearly disappears already at 600 °C. However, weak residual C=O features persist even at higher temperatures, mirroring the XPS-detected oxygen content. These residual signals likely originate from oxygen incorporated within the diamond lattice as the surface C=O moieties are efficiently removed by the annealing in hydrogen, as shown, e.g., on the HPHT ND.

Figure 6. FTIR spectra of the HPHT ND (a), DND low_N (b) and DND (c) as a function of the hydrogenation temperature in °C. The spectra of the initial, oxidized NDs are displayed at the bottom in black (Ox.).

The characteristic features of the hydrogenated DND class are already evident in Figure 6 in the form of broad O–H stretching ($2800\text{--}3700\text{ cm}^{-1}$), superposed with C–H stretches ($2800\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$), and O–H bending ($1550\text{--}1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$) bands, typically attributed to surface-adsorbed or confined water[3,35,54]. These features are observed exclusively for DND and are absent in HPHT ND and DND low_N. Beyond the O–H region, differences are also evident in the fingerprint region ($800\text{--}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$). However, due to the wide temperature range and the superposition of multiple spectral changes in Figure 6, a more detailed comparison of the individual nanodiamond types requires inspection of representative spectra under identical hydrogenation conditions. Figure 7a, therefore, compares the full range FTIR spectra of HPHT ND, DND low_N, and DND hydrogenated at 800 °C in detail. Under these conditions, both HPHT ND and DND low_N exhibit clean C–H stretching bands with no discernible or only very weak O–H or C=O features, whereas DND retains strong absorption in the $800\text{--}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region together with pronounced water-related vibrations and a

distinct sharp band at 3695 cm^{-1} . In our earlier work[3], this feature was tentatively assigned to a “free O–H” vibration associated with hydrophobic patches on the hydrogen-terminated DND surface. The present comparison, however, shows that the 3695 cm^{-1} band is specific to DND and is absent in DND low_N, ruling out a generic hydrophobic origin. We therefore reassign this feature to O–H stretching vibrations of bicarbonate-related (HCO_3^-) surface adsorbates[55,56] stabilized at nitrogen-related surface sites, as discussed in detail below. Figure 7b compares the C–H stretching region of HPHT ND, DND low_N, and DND. HPHT ND and DND low_N exhibit a set of sharp, well-resolved absorption bands at $2835\text{--}2875\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $2920\text{--}2942\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (grey markers), characteristic of well-defined hydrogen termination on ordered diamond facets. Based on established assignments[57], bands in the lower-frequency range ($\approx 2835\text{--}2856\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are primarily associated with monohydrogenated C–H species on (111) diamond surfaces, whereas the higher-frequency group around $2915\text{--}2930\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds predominantly to dihydrogenated C–H₂ configurations characteristic of (100) facets. In contrast, DND displays a markedly different spectral profile, dominated by two broader features centered around $\sim 2850\text{--}2870\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 2920\text{--}2940\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (olive markers), while several bands characteristic of HPHT ND and DND low_N are strongly attenuated or absent. This behavior points to a broader distribution of local C–H bonding environments in DND compared to nitrogen-poor nanodiamonds.

Figure 7. FTIR spectra of hydrogenated HPHT ND, DND low_N, and nitrogen-rich DND after hydrogenation at $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. (a) Full range IR spectra shown with vertical offsets for clarity. (b) Enlarged view of the C–H stretching region, highlighting bands characteristic of HPHT ND and DND low_N (grey markers) and features dominant in DND (olive markers). Peak positions

are indicated at 2835, 2845, and 2856 cm^{-1} (grey) and 2875 cm^{-1} (olive) in the lower-wavenumber region, and at 2920 and 2930 cm^{-1} (grey) and 2942 cm^{-1} (olive) in the higher-wavenumber region.

A further spectral feature observed exclusively for hydrogenated DNDs emerges near 1330 cm^{-1} . This Raman-like absorption coincides with the frequency of the diamond optical phonon, which is nominally infrared-inactive in bulk diamond. In contrast, hydrogenated HPHT NDs do not exhibit a comparable positive absorption feature under the present experimental conditions, although previous studies have reported either a transmission window or interference-like response at a similar frequency, indicating a dependence on the IR measurement geometry and sample configuration [17,58,59].

The presence or absence of spectral signatures around 1330 cm^{-1} therefore depends sensitively on both the nanodiamond type and the experimental implementation of the IR experiment. For DNDs, the emergence of this feature correlates with substantial modification of the surface chemical environment, in particular upon hydrogenation. Traditionally, this feature has been interpreted as arising from local symmetry breaking of diamond C–C bonds, induced by impurities or chemisorbed species, which activates the diamond phonon in IR spectroscopy[48,60]. More recently, Aleksenskii *et al.*[56] refined this interpretation by assigning absorption in this spectral region to carbonate-related surface species, drawing on more recent insights into hydrated carbonate clusters[55].

While existing interpretations provide valuable insight, the present results demonstrate a systematic dependence of the 1330 cm^{-1} feature on nanodiamond type, surface chemistry, and hydrogenation temperature. Its origin and potential links to surface charging and local electronic structure are discussed in detail below.

3.4.2. Temperature- and Substrate-Dependent FTIR Measurements and MS Desorption of H₂O and CO₂

To further examine the thermal stability and origin of the water-related and fingerprint-region features observed by transmission FTIR, temperature-dependent DRIFTS measurements, ATR FTIR, and substrate-dependent FTIR measurements in SAGA mode were performed on fully hydrogenated DND (700°C) and HPHT ND (800°C) samples (Figure 8).

Figures 8a–c present DRIFTS spectra of DNDs recorded between 25 and 250 °C. The full spectra (Fig. 8a) are dominated by intense C–H stretching bands in the 2800–3000 cm^{-1} region, whose positions and intensities remain essentially unchanged over the entire temperature range, indicating a high thermal stability of the hydrogenated diamond surface under the experimental conditions (a nitrogen atmosphere). In contrast, broad O–H stretching features extending from approximately 3000 to 3600 cm^{-1} show a pronounced temperature dependence (Fig. 8b). These bands are strongest at low temperatures and

progressively decrease upon heating, becoming strongly suppressed above $\sim 150\text{--}200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ due to gradual surface water desorption. A sharp feature near 3695 cm^{-1} , previously identified in FTIR spectra of DNDs, follows the same temperature trend and diminishes upon heating.

In the fingerprint region, several temperature-sensitive features are observed between 1250 and 1450 cm^{-1} (Fig. 8c). For clarity, the spectra in this region are normalized to the C–H stretching band at $\sim 2940\text{ cm}^{-1}$, assumed to be temperature-independent. A distinct band centered at $\sim 1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is clearly visible at low and intermediate temperatures and gradually decreases in intensity upon heating, becoming weak at higher temperatures. Additional bands and shoulders in the $1350\text{--}1450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range exhibit a similar but not identical temperature evolution, suggesting the presence of multiple surface-related species with different thermal stabilities. Notably, all these features are strongly suppressed once the O–H-related bands have largely disappeared, indicating a close link between surface hydration and the fingerprint-region response. Temperature-dependent DRIFTS measurements performed on DND low_N and HPHT ND did not reveal a comparable evolution in this region. Figure 8d shows ATR-FTIR spectra of fully hydrogenated DND powder recorded at room temperature using a diamond ATR crystal under two different surface-equilibration conditions. In the first case, the spectrum was acquired for a sample equilibrated with ambient air, i.e., containing adsorbed atmospheric moisture and a natural concentration of CO_2 . In the second case, the same sample was first heated directly on the ATR crystal to remove surface-bound species and subsequently exposed to a flow of CO_2 -free Ar passed through a water bubbler, resulting in controlled readsorption of H_2O in the absence of CO_2 . Several distinct absorption features, highlighted by arrows, are observed only for the air-equilibrated sample. These include bands near $\sim 836, \sim 1000, \sim 1330,$ and $\sim 1390\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the fingerprint region, as well as the sharp O–H-related band at $\sim 3695\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Based on their spectral positions and correlated appearance, these features are consistent with vibrational modes of surface-stabilized bicarbonate species (HCO_3^-), including O–C–O bending modes ($\sim 830\text{--}880\text{ cm}^{-1}$), O–C–O stretching modes ($\sim 1300\text{--}1450\text{ cm}^{-1}$), and weakly hydrogen-bonded O–H stretching vibrations at high wavenumbers. A similar assignment of carbonate- or bicarbonate-related surface species has previously been proposed for hydrogenated nanodiamonds by Aleksenskii *et al.*[56], based on the concept of hydrated carbonate clusters[55]. The exact positions of these bands are expected to depend on the local surface charge and electrostatic environment, which may induce shifts relative to bicarbonate species in bulk or aqueous systems. It should be noted that the strongly structured, “tooth-like” spectral region between approximately 1800 and 2700 cm^{-1} originates from multiphonon absorption of the diamond ATR crystal and does not reflect vibrational features of the sample; this region is therefore excluded from further interpretation. The Raman-like feature at $\sim 1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$, marked by a thicker arrow, coincides with the diamond optical

phonon frequency and is consistently observed only under conditions where CO₂-derived surface species are present.

Figure 8. Infrared response of DND and HPHT NDs. Whole-range temperature-dependent DRIFTS spectra of DND recorded between 25 and 250 °C under N₂ atmosphere (a). High-wavenumber region (2600–4000 cm⁻¹) highlighting the temperature evolution of O–H and C–H stretching bands (b). Normalized fingerprint region (1250–1450 cm⁻¹) showing the temperature-dependent evolution of the ~1330 cm⁻¹ feature in DND (c). ATR-FTIR spectra of DND powder measured at room temperature after equilibration with ambient air (H₂O + CO₂) and after CO₂-free H₂O readsorption; arrows mark CO₂-related bands (~836, ~1330, ~1390, and ~3695 cm⁻¹) (d). The structured region between ~1800 and 2700 cm⁻¹ originates from multiphonon absorption in the ATR crystal. Normalized SAGA FTIR full-range spectra of HPHT NDs deposited on Al and Au substrates (e). Zoomed view of the 1250–1450 cm⁻¹ region highlighting the substrate-dependent response near 1330 cm⁻¹ (f).

Figures 8e–f present SAGA FTIR spectra of fully hydrogenated HPHT NDs deposited on Al and Au substrates. In the full-range spectra (Fig. 8e), HPHT NDs exhibit strong and well-defined C–H stretching bands on both substrates. However, when deposited on Au, additional oxygen-related features, including weak O–H and C=O bands, are observed, whereas these signals are absent or below the detection limit for the same material deposited on Al. In the fingerprint region (Fig. 8f), a pronounced substrate-dependent response is observed around

1330 cm^{-1} : HPHT NDs on Al show a weak positive feature, whereas the same material on Au exhibits a distinct negative feature (“transmission window”) centered at approximately the same wavenumber. Apart from this region, the spectra remain largely featureless and do not show notable temperature- or adsorbate-induced changes under the applied experimental conditions.

cThe persistence and temperature dependence differences in the water- and CO_2 -related infrared features motivated a complementary MS analysis of DND and HPHT ND thermal desorption behavior.

Figure 9. MS desorption profiles of H_2O ($m/z = 18$) and CO_2 ($m/z = 44$) from ambient-equilibrated DND and HPHT ND powders. The ion-current signals were baseline-corrected and subsequently normalized to the specific surface area ($\text{SSA} = 340$ and $95 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for DND and HPHT ND, respectively).

Figure 9 shows the desorption profiles of molecular masses $m/z = 18$ (H_2O) and $m/z = 44$ (CO_2) recorded during heating of ambient-equilibrated DND and HPHT ND powders. The signals were normalized first to sample mass and subsequently to the specific surface area (SSA), using estimated SSA values of $\approx 340 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for DND and $\approx 95 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for HPHT ND, derived from their typical particle sizes ($\sim 5 \text{ nm}$ and $\sim 18 \text{ nm}$, respectively). The DND sample exhibits two distinct water-desorption regimes: a dominant peak centered at $\sim 125 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ followed by a broader feature extending to $\sim 200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and a secondary release between 250

and 340 °C. These events can be attributed to weakly physisorbed water and more strongly bound or confined water associated with polar surface functionalities.

In parallel, CO₂ desorption from DND shows multiple broad maxima that closely follow the water-release regions. This correlation mirrors the infrared observations of persistent O–H- and CO₂-related vibrational features and confirms that CO₂ is stabilized at the DND surface in intimate association with the adsorbed water layer. Such behavior is consistent with CO₂ being partially dissolved in surface-bound water and retained at basic surface sites, most plausibly in the form of carbonate (CO₃²⁻) or bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) hydrated species. The concerted evolution of H₂O and CO₂ signals in MS thus provides independent support and confidence for the FTIR-based assignment of CO₂-derived surface species on hydrogenated DND.

In contrast, the HPHT ND sample exhibits only a weak, narrow H₂O desorption peak at ~80–120 °C and no discernible CO₂ signal over the measured temperature range. This behavior indicates limited water uptake and negligible CO₂ retention, in agreement with the absence of CO₂-related infrared features and the largely invariant FTIR response of hydrogenated HPHT NDs. The low-nitrogen DND sample was not measured, as its structural and colloidal characteristics closely resemble those of HPHT ND, and it was therefore expected to exhibit similar desorption behavior.

In short, the combined FTIR and MS results highlight a clear contrast between DND and HPHT nanodiamonds. DNDs are characterized by persistent surface hydration and the presence of CO₂-related adsorbates, accompanied by temperature- and equilibration-dependent features in the fingerprint region, including the ~1330 cm⁻¹ band, as well as correlated release of H₂O and CO₂ upon heating. In contrast, HPHT nanodiamonds exhibit low water affinity, negligible CO₂ retention, and largely invariant infrared spectra, while still showing a pronounced substrate-dependent response near 1330 cm⁻¹. The occurrence of spectrally distinct yet frequency-coincident features at ~1330 cm⁻¹ in both systems points to an ambiguity of this spectral region, where frequency coincidence alone does not necessarily imply a common microscopic origin.

3.5. Zeta potential and work function evolution

Figure 10a shows the evolution of the zeta potential and work function of HPHT ND, DND low_N, and DND as a function of hydrogenation temperature. All work-function values were measured after mild annealing at 120 °C for 30 min, providing a reproducible and well-defined reference surface state with minimized contributions from weakly adsorbed water.

Figure 10. Evolution of work function and zeta potential of DND, DND low_N, and HPHT ND as a function of hydrogenation temperature (a). Time-dependent recovery of the work function after mild annealing at 120 °C for 30 min, corresponding to re-adsorption of water and air-borne contaminants (b).

Across all ND types, the evolution of the zeta potential broadly follows the progressive surface deoxygenation observed by XPS (Figure 3b) and FTIR spectroscopy (Figure 6). In general, the transition from negative to strongly positive ζ -potentials coincides with the suppression of oxygen-containing surface functionalities and the gradual establishment of hydrogen termination.

A notable exception to this simple correlation is observed for DND. Despite retaining a substantial oxygen content of approximately 6 at.% after hydrogenation at 500 °C (Figure 3b), DNDs already exhibit strongly positive ζ -potentials approaching +50–60 mV (Figure 10a). This contrasts with HPHT ND and DND low_N, which reach comparably high ζ -potential values only after more extensive deoxygenation at higher hydrogenation temperatures.

FTIR spectroscopy indicates that this early onset of positive ζ -potential in DNDs is accompanied by pronounced changes in the nature of oxygen-containing surface groups. Already at 500 °C, the intensity of carbonyl-related vibrations is significantly reduced and the dominant C=O stretching band shifts from the characteristic carboxyl region ($\sim 1780\text{--}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) toward lower wavenumbers ($\sim 1720\text{ cm}^{-1}$), consistent with the transformation or partial reduction of strongly acidic surface groups (Figure 6). This modification effectively

suppresses the contribution of negatively charged functionalities that dominate the ζ -potential of oxidized nanodiamonds, even though a non-negligible amount of oxygen remains on the surface.

Comparison of the two detonation-derived nanodiamond materials reveals an additional systematic distinction. Over the entire hydrogenation-temperature range, the ζ -potential of DND is consistently higher than that of DND low_N by approximately 10–20 mV, and only DND maintains ζ -potential values exceeding +50 mV across a broad temperature window. In contrast, DND low_N exhibits a more gradual increase of ζ -potential with hydrogenation temperature and reaches its maximum at approximately 1000 °C.

Including HPHT ND in the comparison highlights a converging trend. The overall temperature evolution of the ζ -potential in HPHT ND closely resembles that of DND low_N, albeit at systematically higher absolute values. In HPHT ND, the increase of the ζ -potential is delayed and requires higher hydrogenation temperatures (>600 °C), with a maximum reached at approximately 1100 °C. At this temperature, the ζ -potential values of HPHT ND approach those of fully hydrogenated DND, despite the substantially lower nitrogen content of the HPHT material.

The obtained results indicate that while nitrogen incorporation strongly enhances the magnitude and accelerates the emergence of the positive surface charge within the DND class, the position of the ζ -potential maximum is governed primarily by the attainment of optimal surface conditions for charge formation and stabilization, rather than by nitrogen content alone. Consequently, similarly high ζ -potential values can also be achieved in nitrogen-poor HPHT NDs through hydrogenation at elevated temperatures associated with an increased non-diamond carbon content (see the Raman spectra in Figure 5). However, at the highest hydrogenation temperature of 1300 °C, a decrease in the ζ -potential is observed for all samples. This drop coincides with pronounced graphitization, as evidenced by Raman spectroscopy (Figure 5), indicating that excessive structural degradation counteracts the mechanisms responsible for charge stabilization at the hydrogenated surface.

The work-function evolution shows a related but not strictly inverse trend. All oxidized nanodiamonds initially exhibit high work-function values of approximately 5.8–6.0 eV. Upon hydrogenation, the work function decreases markedly for all samples, reaching minima in the range of ~4.5–4.8 eV at intermediate hydrogenation temperatures. This decrease correlates with surface deoxygenation (XPS, Figure 3b), the disappearance of oxygen-related vibrational bands (FTIR, Figure 6), and the formation of a hydrogen-terminated surface.

With further increase of the hydrogenation temperature, the work function gradually rises again. This increase becomes most pronounced above ~1100–1200 °C and coincides with the progressive graphitization detected by Raman spectroscopy (Figure 5). While the absolute work-function values and the temperature at which minima occur differ slightly

among DND, DND low_N, and HPHT ND, the overall evolution reflects a common balance between surface hydrogenation, oxygen removal, and high-temperature structural changes. Figure 9b shows the time-dependent recovery of the work function after mild annealing at 120 °C. In all cases, the work function gradually increases upon exposure to ambient conditions, reflecting re-adsorption of water and airborne contaminants[3]. The recovery kinetics are comparable for HPHT ND and DND low_N but are noticeably faster for DND, indicating a higher affinity of the hydrogenated DND surface for atmospheric species, consistent with its higher surface polarity and stronger interaction with atmospheric species inferred from FTIR and MS measurements.

The concurrent evolution of zeta potential and work function demonstrates that hydrogenation-induced lowering of the work function is a prerequisite for the emergence of a positive surface charge on nanodiamonds. While this trend is observed for all ND materials, the comparison within the detonation-derived nanodiamonds shows that the presence of nitrogen leads to a systematic amplification of the positive zeta potential. These results establish a direct link between surface electronic properties and interfacial chemical reactivity, forming the basis for the mechanistic interpretation discussed below.

3.6. Photothermal CO₂ reduction

By systematically linking surface hydration, CO₂ adsorption, surface charge, and work function, our analysis establishes a unified view of the surface-electronic properties of hydrogenated NDs, providing a mechanistic context to recent reports on photo-assisted CO₂ conversion using hydrogenated DND-based electrodes [13,61,62] and a complementary study on CO₂ photoreduction over oxidized DND[9]. On this basis, we next assess how the described physico-chemical properties of different ND manifest in gas-phase CO₂ reduction.

Figure 11 summarizes the CO production rates obtained during gas-phase CO₂ reduction with H₂ over hydrogenated DND and HPHT ND under thermal-only, photo-only, and combined photothermal conditions. In all experiments, CO was the sole detected carbon-containing product.

Figure 11. Photoreduction properties of HPHT ND and DND samples under thermal, photo, and photothermal conditions.

Under thermal-only conditions, both nanodiamond materials exhibit measurable catalytic activity. The nitrogen-rich DND shows a higher CO production rate than HPHT ND, indicating more efficient CO₂ activation in the absence of illumination. This difference is consistent with the distinct surface chemistries of the two materials and their different affinities toward CO₂, as evidenced by FTIR and MS analyses.

Under photo-only conditions, a clear qualitative difference is observed between the two samples. While HPHT ND exhibits detectable CO formation, DND shows no measurable activity within the sensitivity of the experiment. Moreover, the photo-induced activity of HPHT ND remains lower than its activity under thermal-only conditions.

When heat and light are applied simultaneously, a pronounced enhancement of catalytic activity is observed for HPHT ND. Under photothermal conditions, HPHT ND reaches a CO production rate of approximately 0.021 μmol g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹, corresponding to a roughly 50% increase compared to DND and a clear improvement relative to both thermal-only and photo-only operation. This behavior demonstrates a synergistic effect between thermal activation and illumination for HPHT ND.

In contrast, the activity of DND under photothermal conditions closely matches its thermal-only performance, with no detectable enhancement upon illumination. Thus, while DND is active for thermally driven CO₂ reduction, the addition of light does not lead to a synergistic increase in CO production.

While the overall CO₂ conversion rates remain modest, the results clearly demonstrate that photothermal activity is strongly dependent on the ND type. Differences between DND and HPHT ND directly reflect their distinct surface electronic characteristics and CO₂ sorption behavior established above, which govern the extent to which illumination can synergistically enhance thermally driven surface reactions.

4. Discussion

Before addressing the role of nitrogen in governing surface charging and interfacial reactivity, it is important to clarify the contribution of oxygen detected in all nanodiamond samples. XPS analysis consistently reveals residual oxygen even after hydrogen annealing at temperatures above 800 °C (Fig. 3b), where chemically active surface-bound oxygen functionalities are expected to be efficiently removed. Recent studies have shown that hydrogen-terminated diamond surfaces undergo rapid partial oxidation upon exposure to ambient conditions or aqueous electrolytes, even in the presence of trace moisture[31]. Accordingly, the low oxygen contents detected for low-N DND and HPHT nanodiamonds likely reflect minor post-annealing oxidation of a small fraction of surface C–H bonds upon air exposure.

However, FTIR spectra reveal a distinctly higher contribution of carbonyl-related bands in DND (Figure 6), indicating that a substantial fraction of oxygen in this material is retained in subsurface or bulk-related configurations, such as carbonyl species associated with lattice defects, grain boundaries, or internal interfaces. This interpretation is consistent with the higher oxygen levels detected by XPS for DND compared to other nanodiamond classes (Figure 3b). Such oxygen species, while spectroscopically detectable, are not expected to participate in interfacial protonation equilibria or to account for the specific interfacial behavior observed for DND, nor for the positive ζ-potentials observed across all nanodiamond samples. Oxygen-containing functionalities on nanodiamond surfaces are generally acidic or neutral and typically promote negative or weakly pH-dependent electrokinetic responses.

4.1. Nitrogen in nanodiamonds: structural and electronic context

Nitrogen in DND is predominantly incorporated within the sp³ diamond lattice rather than segregated at the outer surface, as demonstrated by AC-TEM, EELS, ELNES, and EPR studies[19,39,40]. Compared with HPHT nanodiamonds, DNDs contain nitrogen at orders-of-magnitude higher concentrations, which increases the probability of local nitrogen pairing, clustering, and association with lattice defects, particularly in smaller particles[63]. Owing to the extremely small size of DNDs, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy does not probe solely the outermost atomic layers but effectively averages over a substantial fraction

of the particle volume. Consequently, the N 1s signal reflects contributions from both bulk-embedded and near-surface nitrogen species.

In DNDs, two N 1s components are consistently observed at binding energies of 398–399 eV and around 402 eV. The dominant component at 398–399 eV is most reasonably assigned to nitrogen incorporated in an sp^3 carbon environment, commonly described as substitutional or defect-associated C–N configurations within the diamond lattice[19,39]. This assignment is supported by its persistence upon hydrogenation and thermal treatment, in agreement with earlier spectroscopic and microscopic studies[20]. Importantly, this dominant nitrogen species shows a systematic correlation with surface basicity, hydration behavior, ζ -potential, and CO_2 affinity. Although such lattice-embedded nitrogen atoms do not constitute classical Brønsted bases, their presence locally perturbs the electronic structure of the diamond lattice, increasing the electron density and polarizability in the near-surface region. This electronically active nitrogen facilitates interfacial charge compensation and stabilization, which manifests experimentally as enhanced hydration, positive ζ -potential, and a strong affinity toward CO_2 -derived surface species. This interpretation also rationalizes the persistence of a positive ζ -potential in partially graphitized DNDs, where classical surface functional groups are largely absent [29].

By contrast, the weaker N 1s contribution at higher binding energies (~ 402 eV) likely reflects a minor fraction of nitrogen atoms in oxidized, protonated, or strongly polarized local environments, potentially associated with subsurface or electronically depleted N–C–O configurations [64]. In these species, the nitrogen lone-pair density is either strongly withdrawn or spatially inaccessible, rendering them spectroscopically detectable but largely inactive with respect to interfacial charge stabilization and surface basicity at the solid–liquid interface.

These observations indicate that the distinct interfacial behavior of DNDs, and the broader differences among nanodiamond classes originate primarily from electronically active, lattice-embedded nitrogen.

4.1.1. Nitrogen-induced lattice disorder and thermal stability

Raman spectroscopy shows that the evolution of lattice disorder across HPHT ND, DND low_N, and nitrogen-rich DND is governed primarily by nitrogen incorporation rather than by particle size effects. The progressive red shift, broadening, and increasing asymmetry of the diamond phonon with increasing nitrogen content are characteristic signatures of defect-induced perturbations of the sp^3 lattice, well documented for nitrogen-doped[65] and irradiation-damaged[17,52] diamond systems. Given that the characteristic crystallite sizes of both DND and DND low_N exceed the regime where phonon confinement becomes prominent[20,51], the observed Raman spectra differences can be attributed to enhanced phonon scattering on nitrogen-related point defects, local strain fields, and associated

electronic perturbations that shorten the phonon mean free path and break local lattice symmetry[66]. This demonstrates that nitrogen concentration is the dominant factor controlling the apparent diamond quality in Raman spectra.

Nitrogen-dependent trends are also reflected in the sp^2 -related Raman features. The enhanced contribution near $\sim 1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in DND indicates a higher density of isolated, strained sp^2 sites stabilized within defective regions of the lattice, whereas the comparatively stronger $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ contribution in DND low_N is consistent with more extended, surface- or grain-boundary-associated sp^2 carbon. Together, these observations confirm that nitrogen incorporation promotes both lattice disorder and defect-stabilized non- sp^3 configurations in detonation nanodiamonds.

4.1.2. Nitrogen effects on thermal stability under hydrogen

The thermal transformation of DND has been extensively studied under inert or vacuum conditions, where surface reconstruction into graphitic layers occurs below $\sim 900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, followed by progressive graphitization of the diamond core at higher temperatures and eventual formation of carbon onions[53,67,68].

Under hydrogen, the degradation mechanism differs fundamentally. Hydrogen annealing proceeds through radical-mediated pathways in which defect-rich sp^2 regions catalyze the dissociation of molecular hydrogen, generating reactive H radicals[47,48] that hydrogenate and etch carbon fragments. As a result, newly formed sp^2 carbon is preferentially converted into volatile hydrocarbons rather than reorganizing into stable graphitic shells, effectively lowering the apparent thermal stability of nanodiamonds under reductive conditions.

Consistent with this mechanism, DND exhibits an earlier onset of mass loss and structural degradation than DND low_N and HPHT ND, as evidenced by thermogravimetric analysis and XPS (Figure 3), and Raman spectroscopy (Figure 5). Nitrogen incorporation introduces lattice strain and increases the density of defect-mediated sp^2 sites that act as initiation centers for hydrogen dissociation and subsequent gasification. Consequently, DND begins to degrade at $\sim 800\text{--}900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, whereas DND low_N and HPHT ND retain structural integrity up to $\sim 1000\text{--}1100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under identical hydrogenation conditions.

The close agreement between Raman-detected graphitization, mass-loss profiles, and XPS-derived sp^2 evolution demonstrates that nitrogen content, rather than particle size or intrinsic disorder alone, reduces the thermal stability of DND under hydrogen. DND low_N and HPHT ND preserve a sufficiently ordered sp^3 framework to withstand hydrogen-assisted etching to higher temperatures, defining a practical upper limit for hydrogen annealing and high-temperature functional applications. At the same time, the reduced thermal stability of DND highlights an inherent trade-off: nitrogen enhances surface reactivity and hydrogenation efficiency but compromises structural endurance at elevated temperatures.

4.2. Hydrogen termination of diamond as a common platform

In line with previous studies on both detonation and HPHT-derived nanodiamonds, hydrogenation induces a systematic transformation of the nanodiamond surface that is largely independent of the synthesis route. Early work on single-crystal diamond and nanodiamond systems has demonstrated that hydrogen termination efficiently removes oxygen-related surface functional groups, profoundly modifies the surface electronic structure by lowering the electron affinity, and enables charge-transfer processes mediated by surface adsorbates and interfacial water layers[69–71]. Consistently, our XPS and FTIR data show that all investigated nanodiamond types undergo progressive deoxygenation and formation of C–H terminated surfaces within a comparable temperature window.

In this sense, hydrogen termination provides a shared baseline that enables comparison of the electronic and colloidal behavior of different nanodiamond materials. Importantly, the data show that the fundamental ability to form a hydrogenated surface state is not the primary differentiating factor between HPHT ND, DND low_N, and DND. Instead, the experimentally observed differences in zeta potential, hydration behavior, adsorption of CO₂-related species, and electronic response arise from how this common hydrogen-terminated platform is modulated by lattice quality, defect density, and nitrogen incorporation. In other words, while hydrogenation establishes the same chemical starting point for all nanodiamonds, the subsequent surface functionality is governed by material-specific structural and electronic characteristics, which are unified and discussed mechanistically in the following sections.

4.3. Unified picture of surface charging in hydrogenated nanodiamonds

The results presented here demonstrate that surface charging in H-NDs cannot be rationalized within classical acid–base models of ζ -potential formation. Hydrogen-terminated nanodiamond surfaces are dominated by nonpolar C–H_x groups and lack dissociable functional moieties capable of generating charge through protonation–deprotonation equilibria. Accordingly, the positive ζ -potential must originate from an electronically driven interfacial mechanism associated with charge transfer and interfacial polarization.

This interpretation builds on our previous study of hydrogenated HPHT nanodiamonds with minimal sp² surface contribution, where we showed that such materials exhibit the smallest positive ζ -potential at their native pH and the least robust colloidal stability upon increasing pH[17,37]. These observations were attributed to the limited availability of surface-proximal electronic acceptor states capable of stabilizing transferred charge, despite hydrogen termination.

Among the nanodiamond systems investigated here, HPHT nanodiamonds represent the closest structural and electronic analogue to bulk diamond. However, unlike bulk diamond

surfaces typically hydrogenated by plasma treatments, nanodiamonds are hydrogenated thermally, a process that inevitably induces partial surface restructuring through radical-mediated desorption of the original surface functional groups[47]. As a consequence, even structurally well-ordered HPHT nanodiamonds deviate from the ideal atomic arrangement of a perfectly hydrogen-terminated diamond surface and inherently develop a finite density of localized surface-derived electronic states, hereafter referred to as *intrinsic surface states*.

Within this framework, surface transfer doping, well established for hydrogenated bulk diamond, provides a unifying electronic basis for positive ζ -potential formation in hydrogenated nanodiamonds. Hydrogen termination lowers the surface energetic barrier and enables electron transfer from the diamond lattice toward acceptor states in the near-surface region, leading to electron depletion within the sp^3 diamond core. While charge transfer at ideal, plasma-hydrogenated bulk diamond surfaces is predominantly governed by external acceptors in the adjacent environment[22], thermally hydrogenated nanodiamonds inherently host intrinsic surface states that can act as local electron acceptors.

Electron localization in these intrinsic surface states results in intraparticle charge polarization, characterized by hole formation in the diamond core and negative charge accumulation near the surface. In HPHT nanodiamonds, these holes remain at least partially mobile, consistent with the correlated evolution of Fano-type FTIR signatures and enhanced electrical conductivity reported previously[17]. Electrostatic compensation of the localized negative surface charge by excess protons in the adjacent aqueous phase gives rise to the experimentally observed positive ζ -potential. Protonation of sp^2 -rich surface domains, previously described phenomenologically[36], therefore represents the electrostatic counterpart of this electron-transfer process rather than an independent charging mechanism. In this sense, the models proposed by Petit *et al.* [29,35] and Ginés *et al.* [36] describe complementary manifestations of the same electronically driven interfacial phenomenon.

Experimental support for this unified picture is provided by the coexistence of well-defined diamond C–H terminations observed by FTIR (Figure 7) and sp^2 -related signatures detected by Raman spectroscopy (Figure 6), indicating a highly heterogeneous surface where atomically ordered hydrogenated diamond sites coexist with structurally and electronically perturbed regions hosting the intrinsic surface states. The evolution of the ζ -potential with hydrogenation temperature in HPHT nanodiamonds further substantiates this interpretation, exhibiting a pronounced maximum at approximately 1100 °C (Figure 10). In the temperature window between \approx 800 and 1100 °C, hydrogen termination is already complete and remains well preserved, while the density of intrinsic surface states increases, allowing systematic tuning of the surface charge density and ζ -potential up to an optimum

value before extensive graphitization and particle degradation set in. This balance is schematically summarized in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Schematic representation of the electronically driven mechanism responsible for positive ζ -potential in hydrogenated HPHT NDs. Complete hydrogen termination is established at ≈ 800 °C, while increasing the hydrogenation temperature up to 1100 °C enhances the density of localized intrinsic surface states, promoting electron transfer into intrinsic surface states, interfacial polarization, and proton compensation in the Stern layer. The resulting surface charge density and ζ -potential reach a maximum at ≈ 1100 °C, before extensive graphitization at higher temperatures reduces the effectiveness of this mechanism.

The relative importance and spatial distribution of ordered hydrogenated sites and intrinsic surface states differ markedly among the investigated nanodiamond types. While HPHT ND and DND low_N retain sufficiently ordered surfaces to preserve facet-specific C–H vibrational signatures, DNDs exhibit a higher density of defect-adjacent and electronically perturbed sites, resulting in broadened C–H stretching features and a more diffuse vibrational response (Figure 7b). This indicates that, in DNDs, hydrogen termination occurs on a structurally and electronically more heterogeneous surface, where local charge localization, defect chemistry, and intrinsic surface states jointly modulate the interfacial electronic structure.

Despite exhibiting the lowest work-function values (Figure 10) and complete hydrogen termination (Figure 6), DND low_N develops significantly lower ζ -potentials than HPHT NDs. This observation suggests that, beyond energetic alignment, the efficiency of surface transfer doping is critically governed by the structural and electronic quality of the near-

surface region. In structurally disordered DND low_N, the high density of defects and lattice distortions likely reduces the effectiveness of the charge transfer into intrinsic surface states and limits the stabilization of localized surface charge. As a result, fewer transferred electrons contribute to sustained interfacial polarization, leading to a diminished ζ -potential compared to the more structurally coherent HPHT NDs. The systematic differences observed between HPHT ND, DND low_N, and DND therefore do not imply distinct surface-charging mechanisms, but rather reflect how a shared electronically driven process, surface transfer doping tightly coupled to intrinsic surface states, is modulated by nanoscale structural and electronic heterogeneity. Additional material-specific contributions, particularly those associated with nitrogen incorporation, are addressed in the following section.

4.4. Nitrogen-assisted charging in detonation nanodiamonds

While hydrogen termination and intrinsic surface-derived acceptor states define a common electronic charging mechanism, DNDs exhibit a nitrogen-specific contribution that provides an extra pathway for positive surface charge stabilization, making their interfacial behavior unique among hydrogenated nanodiamonds.

A key experimental manifestation of this nitrogen contribution is the systematically higher zeta potential of DND compared with DND low_N. Across a broad hydrogenation-temperature window, DNDs exhibit ζ -potentials that are typically 10–20 mV higher than those of DND low_N (Figure 10), despite comparable particle size distributions and similar degrees of structural disorder (Figures 1 and 4). This difference persists even when WF values are similar, demonstrating that nitrogen introduces a charging contribution that cannot be explained by surface energetics or transfer-doping efficiency alone.

From a chemical perspective, nitrogen incorporated within DND can act locally at the solid–liquid interface, particularly within electronically active surface regions created upon deoxygenation and hydrogenation. In the vicinity of intrinsic surface states, nitrogen-related basic sites may participate in local acid–base interactions, for example, by stabilizing interfacial protons. In this sense, nitrogen provides an additional, chemically mediated pathway that boosts the magnitude and stability of the electronically generated surface charge. While these electronic and chemical contributions are likely coupled at the nanoscale, their precise interplay cannot be unambiguously disentangled based on the present data.

FTIR, DRIFTS, and MS measurements provide converging evidence that nitrogen-containing DNDs exhibit markedly enhanced surface hydration compared with both DND low_N and HPHT ND. Broad O–H stretching and bending bands, temperature-dependent water desorption, and the persistence of tightly bound hydration features demonstrate that nitrogen promotes the formation of a stable interfacial water layer. This behavior is

consistent with earlier reports of unusually strong water adsorption on hydrogenated DNDs[3,35,54], but, as demonstrated here, is absent in nitrogen-poor NDs, highlighting that hydration enhancement originates from polar, nitrogen-related sites rather than from hydrogen termination alone.

In addition to hydration, nitrogen-containing DNDs display a pronounced affinity toward atmospheric CO₂. FTIR and DRIFTS spectra reveal carbonate- and bicarbonate-related vibrational features, corroborated by MS desorption profiles showing correlated release of H₂O and CO₂ over extended temperature ranges. These observations demonstrate that CO₂ is stabilized at the DND surface via weakly bound carbonate and bicarbonate species, most plausibly associated with protonated nitrogen-containing sites within the hydrated interfacial layer. Aleksenskii *et al.* attributed carbonate adsorption to a generic basicity of hydrogenated nanodiamond surfaces[56]. The present comparative data demonstrate that this behavior is specific to nitrogen-containing DNDs, as it is absent in DND low_N and HPHT ND. Nitrogen, therefore, provides chemically defined binding motifs for CO₂ and other anionic species.

Finally, the role of nitrogen also manifests in the vibrational response of hydrogenated nanodiamonds, most prominently through the appearance of a spectral feature near 1330 cm⁻¹. Importantly, the physical origin of this response differs fundamentally between HPHT NDs and DNDs, reflecting delocalized electronic coupling in the former and adsorbate-dominated surface chemistry in the latter.

Hydrogenated HPHT nanodiamonds are electrically conductive[17], enabling electronic coupling between the nanodiamond layer and the underlying substrate. In substrate-dependent SAGA FTIR measurements, this coupling gives rise to pronounced modulation of the diamond optical phonon near 1330 cm⁻¹, including dip-like or interference features whose sign and magnitude depend sensitively on the supporting metal (Figure 8 e, f). Such behavior is characteristic of Fano-type interference between a discrete lattice vibration and a continuum of electronic states and has been recently reported for conductive H-NDs [17,37,72–74]. In contrast, when HPHT nanodiamonds are measured in transmission geometry on insulating substrates (e.g., CaF₂, Figure 7), no corresponding activation of the diamond phonon is observed, underscoring the decisive role of substrate-mediated electronic coupling.

This substrate dependence can be rationalized in terms of work function mismatch and Fermi level alignment at the metal–nanodiamond interface [75]. For Au, with a typical work function of ~5.1–5.3 eV, electrons are transferred from HPHT NDs (WF ~4.65, Figure 10) into the metal, resulting in electron depletion and the formation of mobile hole states in the near-surface region of the nanodiamond layer[32]. Under these conditions, the discrete diamond optical phonon couples to a continuum of electronic states, giving rise to a characteristic Fano-type interference. This mechanism fully accords with the interpretation proposed by

Kudryatsev *et al.*[72], who first linked dip-like features in the diamond-phonon region to interference between lattice vibrations and delocalized charge carriers in hydrogenated nanodiamond systems. Crucially, this electronically driven scenario is directly corroborated by the infrared spectra themselves. As shown in Figure 8d,e, HPHT NDs deposited on Au exhibit pronounced C=O and O–H vibrational bands, indicating partial oxidation and the formation of hydroxylated surface species, whereas the same nanodiamonds deposited on Al show no such signatures. This observation is fully consistent with recent work by Chemin *et al.*[31], who demonstrated that hydrogen-terminated diamond surfaces undergo spontaneous oxidation once electron depletion and surface band bending enable interfacial redox reactions in aqueous or humid environments. In contrast, Al exhibits a substantially lower work function ($\sim 4.1\text{--}4.3$ eV), favoring electron transfer from the metal into the HPHT ND deposit. However, owing to the wide band gap of diamond and the discrete nature of near-surface electronic states in H-NDs, the injected electrons do not form a delocalized electronic continuum at the Fermi level capable of sustaining strong phonon–carrier coupling. As a result, the diamond-phonon response on Al is significantly weaker and lacks the pronounced interference character observed on Au. The residual, weak feature near 1330 cm^{-1} thus reflects a transition toward a localized charging regime, in which charge stabilization occurs at discrete defect- or impurity-related sites rather than through substrate-mediated electronic coupling.

Unlike HPHT nanodiamonds, detonation nanodiamonds are electrically non-conductive [17], which suppresses long-range charge transport and precludes electronic coupling to the supporting substrate. Their infrared response is therefore insensitive to substrate material and measurement configuration, and the spectral features observed in the $800\text{--}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region must originate from localized surface or near-surface species rather than from charge–phonon interference effects characteristic of electronically coupled diamond systems.

DRIFTS measurements reveal a set of correlated bands at approximately 838, 1195, 1330, 1380, and 1670 cm^{-1} that systematically diminish and disappear upon heating to $150\text{--}200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Figure 8a,c), in parallel with CO_2 desorption detected by TGA–MS (Figure 9). This common thermal evolution strongly indicates a joint chemical origin. The observed band pattern and its temperature-dependent shifts closely match infrared signatures reported for hydrated carbonate and bicarbonate clusters, as reported by Garand and co-workers[55]. In particular, the gradual red-shift and eventual disappearance of the 1330 cm^{-1} band with increasing temperature are consistent with progressive dehydration of bicarbonate species, for which Garand *et al.* reported systematic frequency shifts of the $\nu(\text{C–O})$ modes as the number of coordinating water molecules decreases.

Within this assignment, the individual bands can be rationalized as follows: the feature near 838 cm^{-1} corresponds to out-of-plane bending modes of carbonate/bicarbonate species;

bands around 1195 and 1380 cm^{-1} arise from symmetric and asymmetric C–O stretching modes; and the broad contribution near 1670 cm^{-1} reflects strongly hydrogen-bonded bicarbonate species coupled to interfacial water [55]. Importantly, the frequency of the band near 1330 cm^{-1} exhibits a systematic red shift (1333 to 1320 cm^{-1}) upon increasing the sample temperature during DRIFTS measurements (Figure 8c). This behavior reflects progressive dehydration of surface-stabilized bicarbonate species, i.e., a gradual reduction of the number of water molecules coordinating the bicarbonate anion as temperature increases. Such hydration-dependent frequency shifts are well documented for isolated bicarbonate species, where decreasing hydration leads to a red shift of C–O vibrational modes[55]. By contrast, intrinsic diamond lattice phonons are expected to display only minor, nearly linear temperature-dependent shifts, which are far too small[37,76] to account for the pronounced frequency changes observed here during DRIFTS heating. Thus, the 1330 cm^{-1} band, which has previously been considered controversial and was in earlier work, including our own[63,77], sometimes discussed in terms of nitrogen-induced activation of the diamond lattice, fits naturally into this vibrational manifold as a hydration-sensitive bicarbonate mode.

Ion-exchange experiments reported by Aleksenskii et al.[56] further support this interpretation. Replacement of bicarbonate species by other anions (Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , CH_3COO^-) leads to the disappearance of the carbonate-related bands and the emergence of new vibrational features characteristic of the respective anions, rather than to the persistence of the 1330 cm^{-1} band. This behavior does not indicate reduced electronic activity of these anions, but simply reflects their distinct vibrational spectra. Carbonate species dominate under ambient conditions because CO_2 is naturally present in air and aqueous environments, making carbonate and bicarbonate the thermodynamically favored surface adsorbates on hydrogenated DNDs.

Figure 13. Schematic comparison of surface charging and infrared response mechanisms in hydrogenated nanodiamonds. In HPHT nanodiamonds, hydrogenation enables delocalized charge redistribution and substrate-sensitive phonon–carrier coupling, giving rise to a Fano-type infrared response near the diamond phonon frequency. In detonation-derived nanodiamonds, nitrogen-rich surfaces promote localized charge stabilization and strong hydration, enabling adsorption and stabilization of bicarbonate species. The resulting infrared feature near 1330 cm^{-1} originates from vibrational modes of surface-stabilized carbonate/bicarbonate species and is not directly related to activation of the diamond lattice. DND low_N shows only a weak IR response. Representative experimental IR spectra are shown; the two DND panels share the same intensity scale.

In contrast to HPHT nanodiamonds and DNDs, DND low_N exhibit only a weak spectral response in the diamond-phonon region, with no signatures of substrate-induced electronic coupling. This muted behavior is consistent with the lack of mobile charge carriers required for Fano-type interference effects observed in more crystalline HPHT materials. At the same time, the presence of a weak but discernible feature around 1330 cm^{-1} indicates that a limited population of nitrogen-related basic sites capable of stabilizing hydrated bicarbonate species is still present at the surface. The reduced intensity of this band relative to DNDs, therefore, naturally reflects the lower nitrogen content. The involved mechanisms are schematically depicted in Figure 13.

In summary, the vibrational features observed for DNDs in the 800–1700 cm^{-1} region are consistently explained by the presence of hydrated carbonate and bicarbonate species stabilized at nitrogen-containing surface sites. The $\sim 1330 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ band, in particular, is best described as a bicarbonate-derived vibrational mode whose frequency and intensity are governed by hydration state and thermal equilibration rather than by nitrogen-induced activation or polarization of the diamond lattice. Its coincidence with the diamond optical phonon frequency, previously reported by Lawson and co-workers for positively charged nitrogen centers in bulk nitrogen-doped diamond [78], is striking and initially suggests a possible analogy. However, while such a phonon-related interpretation is well established and physically justified for bulk diamond, the experimental trends observed here, including temperature-dependent frequency shifts during DRIFTS heating, disappearance upon CO_2 desorption, and lack of recovery upon CO_2 -free rehydration, are more consistently explained by a chemical, adsorbate-based origin. In this context, the apparent frequency overlap represents a fortuitous coincidence rather than a causal connection, providing a plausible explanation for the long-standing misassignment of the 1330 cm^{-1} band in DND in the literature. Importantly, although charge separation and nitrogen-related lattice polarization may still occur in hydrogenated DNDs [78], the present data do not require invoking a diamond phonon activation mechanism to rationalize the observed infrared response, in agreement with the interpretation of Aleksenskii et al. [56] and detailed spectroscopic studies of hydrated bicarbonate species[55].

4.5. Implications of nitrogen-assisted surface charging for chemical and photochemical reactivity

The photothermal CO_2 reduction behavior observed here (Figure 11) can be rationalized within the unified structure–surface–electronics framework developed above. H-NDs combine two, in principle independent, ingredients relevant for photothermal CO_2 conversion: (i) diamond-specific surface electronic effects enabled by hydrogen termination and reduced surface energetic barriers (Section 4.3), and (ii) surface chemistry governing CO_2 adsorption and activation, which is particularly pronounced for DND due to nitrogen-assisted interfacial polarity and stabilization of bicarbonate species (Section 4.4).

A central outcome is that neither contribution alone is sufficient to produce photothermal synergy. Strong CO_2 adsorption does not automatically translate into light-enhanced activity, and favorable electronic structure does not guarantee high rates unless charge transfer can be efficiently coupled into surface reactions. This trade-off is directly reflected in the contrast between DND and HPHT ND: DND exhibits higher activity under purely thermal conditions, consistent with strong CO_2 stabilization at basic and hydrated surface

motifs, but shows no measurable enhancement upon illumination. In contrast, HPHT ND displays a clear photothermal enhancement despite weak CO₂ retention, indicating that the rate-limiting step under illumination is linked to light-assisted charge transfer at the hydrogenated diamond surface rather than to CO₂ capture.

In the broader literature, light-driven CO₂ conversion on diamond-based systems is commonly discussed in terms of interfacial electron emission or electron transfer from hydrogenated diamond surfaces, enabled by reduced surface energetic barriers and, in sufficiently ordered systems, negative electron affinity. Yoshikawa and co-workers demonstrated efficient visible-light-driven CO₂ reduction using diamond-based electrodes in which a porous, hydrogenated DND layer is integrated with a boron-doped diamond (BDD) substrate[13,61,62]. In this architecture, the nitrogen-rich, defect-enabled DND layer governs light absorption and charge separation, while the underlying p-type BDD primarily serves as an electron reservoir and transport medium. Nitrogen originating from DND is therefore not treated as a direct chemical active site but rather as a contributor to electronically and structurally perturbed near-surface regions that enable visible-light excitation and efficient charge separation within the DND/BDD p-n junction. At the same time, hydrogen termination remains essential, as oxidized or insufficiently hydrogenated surfaces show strongly suppressed activity. This literature framework is fully consistent with our observations, which indicate that hydrogenation establishes the necessary electronic precondition for charge transfer, while material-specific features, such as nitrogen incorporation and surface heterogeneity, determine how the electronic excitation is ultimately translated into surface chemical reactivity.

From the perspective of the present gas-phase study, the role of DNDs in Yoshikawa's electrode architecture [13] can be interpreted more broadly. While the reported photoelectrochemical activity is primarily discussed in terms of hydrogen-terminated diamond enabling efficient charge injection from the BDD electrode, the potential contribution of nitrogen-containing DNDs to CO₂ adsorption and stabilization has not been explicitly addressed. Our results indicate that basic N-related surface sites can significantly enhance CO₂ uptake and stabilization, suggesting that this chemical functionality may represent an additional, previously unquantified contribution to the overall performance of such electrodes. In this framework, nitrogen-rich DNDs may primarily promote surface concentration and chemical activation of CO₂, whereas the supply of photoexcited electrons is governed by the electronic structure of hydrogenated diamond. This view is consistent with our observation that DNDs excel under purely thermal conditions due to their strong CO₂ affinity, but show limited intrinsic photothermal synergy, whereas HPHT NDs, with superior electronic quality and negative electron affinity, exhibit pronounced light-assisted enhancement despite weaker CO₂ adsorption.

Our results thus reveal a previously underappreciated role of nitrogen in DND as a chemically active, interfacial modifier that promotes CO₂ sorption, surface hydration, and stabilization of charged surface states, thereby enhancing adsorption-driven activation pathways. However, in the absence of efficient long-range charge transport and electronically coherent pathways, hydrogenated DNDs do not exhibit a pronounced intrinsic photothermal synergy under the present reaction conditions.

Beyond providing a mechanistic framework for surface charging in H-DNDs, the present results also offer a basis for reinterpreting several earlier observations reported for DND in chemical and biological contexts. In drug delivery studies employing partially hydrogenated, positively charged DNDs, reversible and pH-dependent binding of doxorubicin has been observed and commonly rationalized in terms of interactions with residual surface carboxyl groups, despite the overall positive ζ -potential [79,80]. Under such conditions, classical carboxyl-mediated binding is unlikely to be the sole interaction pathway. In light of the present results, an additional contribution from localized nitrogen-related basic sites cannot be excluded and may have contributed to doxorubicin binding, particularly given its amphoteric character and pronounced pH sensitivity.

A similar refinement may apply to reports of strong adhesion between hydrogenated DNDs and hydrophobic sp²-carbon materials, where the interaction has been discussed primarily in terms of hydrophobic “bucky” patches combined with electrostatics. The presence of spatially confined basic sites may modulate such interfaces at short length scales, contributing to the unexpectedly strong affinity observed for certain DND–sp² carbon combinations[81].

Perhaps the most compelling example is provided by the exceptionally high-affinity binding of fibroblast growth factor FGF2 to hydrogenated DNDs, reported to occur with nanomolar apparent dissociation constants even in complex biological media[82,83]. Such behavior is difficult to reconcile with a purely global surface charge picture and instead suggests the involvement of chemically heterogeneous surface motifs capable of localized and selective interactions. Nitrogen-associated basic sites embedded within a hydrated interfacial layer provide a natural candidate for such functionality.

Independent support for the importance of nitrogen in modulating interfacial water comes from dielectric and spectroscopic studies of confined water on nanodiamond surfaces. In particular, Batsanov and co-workers[41] reported that low-nitrogen detonation nanodiamonds exhibit markedly different hydration behavior compared to nitrogen-rich DNDs, despite comparable particle size and surface area. While the origin of this difference was not resolved at the time, the present framework offers a straightforward interpretation: in the absence of nitrogen-related surface sites, hydration remains weak and nonspecific, whereas nitrogen enables the stabilization of charged and polarized interfacial water layers.

Within this context, earlier reports of unusually strong perturbations of water structure around fully or partially hydrogenated DND also warrant reconsideration. In particular, the interpretation proposed by Petit et al.[35], invoking electron transfer into antibonding orbitals of water, may alternatively be viewed through the lens of charge stabilization at surface-bound acceptor species, such as bicarbonate ions, which are naturally present under ambient conditions. In this picture, water does not merely act as a passive dielectric medium, but forms an integral part of a coupled interfacial system involving nitrogen-derived basic sites, solvated ions, and surface electronic states.

These considerations suggest that nitrogen-induced local basicity represents an underappreciated but potentially central factor governing molecular, ionic, and biomolecular interactions of DND. Rather than being a generic consequence of hydrogen termination, the chemical reactivity and interfacial behavior of DNDs emerge from a subtle interplay between hydrogen-induced electronic activation and nitrogen-enabled chemical heterogeneity. The present results thus motivate a re-examination of earlier findings on NDs with explicit attention to nitrogen content, surface heterogeneity, and the coupled roles of water and adsorbed ionic species.

Very recently, an independent preprint study[84] reported efficient photocatalytic degradation of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) using hydrogenated, highly crystalline milled nanodiamonds—closely analogous to the HPHT ND investigated here—whereas hydrogenated DNDs remained significantly less active. Importantly, the authors attributed this contrast to differences in electron affinity and surface electronic structure rather than to hydrogen termination alone. In the context of the present work, such electronic differences are naturally expected to be strongly conditioned by the defect-rich nature of DNDs and their markedly higher nitrogen incorporation, both of which can reshape the near-surface electronic landscape and limit efficient photocarrier utilization. These findings therefore provide an application-driven validation of the framework proposed here, highlighting that the electronic consequences of hydrogenation in nanodiamonds are not universal but depend critically on core crystallinity, defect structure, and associated dopant chemistry.

5. Conclusions

This study provides a unified mechanistic framework for understanding surface charging, hydration, and CO₂ interaction in hydrogenated nanodiamonds by disentangling the roles of hydrogenation, lattice quality, and nitrogen incorporation. By introducing low-nitrogen detonation nanodiamonds with a defect structure comparable to conventional DNDs, nitrogen is identified as a key parameter governing surface polarity and interfacial chemistry, beyond the effects of structural disorder alone.

Hydrogenation establishes a common electronic basis for positive ζ -potential formation across all nanodiamond types by inducing surface deoxygenation, lowering the work function, and enabling electron transfer toward near-surface intrinsic acceptor states. This electronically driven process operates irrespective of synthesis route and provides a unifying explanation for positive surface charging in hydrogenated nanodiamonds. Its manifestation, however, is strongly modulated by lattice quality and defect density. In nitrogen-rich DNDs, nitrogen introduces an additional, chemically localized contribution to surface charging. Nitrogen-related basic sites enhance proton stabilization, surface hydration, and CO_2 affinity, leading to systematically higher ζ -potentials and strong adsorption of bicarbonate species. This dual electronic–chemical charging mechanism explains the distinct interfacial behavior of DNDs compared with nitrogen-poor DND and HPHT nanodiamonds.

The spectroscopic response near 1330 cm^{-1} emerges as a particularly illustrative example of this distinction. In HPHT nanodiamonds, the response reflects a physical, diamond-related electronic effect associated with charge redistribution and phonon–carrier coupling at electronically aligned interfaces. In contrast, in DNDs, the same spectral region is dominated by vibrational modes of surface-stabilized hydrated bicarbonate species and therefore has a chemical origin unrelated to intrinsic diamond lattice activation. The apparent frequency coincidence between these fundamentally different phenomena provides a clear explanation for the long-standing ambiguity surrounding the 1330 cm^{-1} feature in detonation nanodiamond literature.

These mechanistic differences are directly reflected in gas-phase CO_2 conversion. Nitrogen-rich DNDs favor thermally driven CO_2 activation through strong surface adsorption and stabilization, whereas HPHT nanodiamonds exhibit pronounced photothermal enhancement enabled by their superior electronic structure and negative-electron-affinity-like surface conditions. Together, these results demonstrate that efficient photothermal CO_2 reduction requires a balance between surface chemical activation and electronically coherent charge transfer, which are not simultaneously optimized in a single nanodiamond system studied here.

Overall, this work establishes a unified model of positive ζ -potential formation in hydrogenated nanodiamonds and highlights nitrogen as a central factor controlling interfacial chemistry through localized stabilization of surface charge, hydration, and adsorbates. By establishing direct links between work function, ζ -potential, vibrational response, and photothermal reactivity, this work positions hydrogenated nanodiamonds as an emerging materials platform for designing electronically and chemically coupled interfaces in advanced photocatalytic and environmental technologies.

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Author contributions (CRediT)

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this manuscript, S. S. used ChatGPT 5.2 (OpenAI) to assist with language editing, clarity of expression, and stylistic refinement of the text. All scientific content, interpretations, and conclusions were developed by the authors, who reviewed and edited the manuscript and take full responsibility for its content.

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Graphical abstract:

- **Hydrogenated nanodiamonds:**
Same chemistry, modulated charge manifestation

